

D2.2 Retrieval model for conversational style queries

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Abstract	<p>This report presents research and experimental developments under WP2, Task 2, focusing on factual information retrieval (FIR) with conversational queries. We address open challenges including enhancing large language model (LLM) efficiency, mitigating hallucinations, identifying bias, and developing methodologies for semi-automatic creation of FIR training and benchmark datasets. Building upon prior work in T2.1, we extend a speech-to-text processing pipeline that enables reuse of existing text-based FIR systems for conversational speech data, using a BGE-M3 multilingual retrieval model. Two alignment strategies between speech and text embeddings are explored, with input-space alignment yielding superior results. Additionally, we propose a methodology for constructing a multimodal QA dataset from natural podcast conversations, advancing resources for FIR on spontaneous speech. Our work also expands on synthetic dataset creation using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques, contributing to better contextualization and trustworthiness of LLM-based systems. Further, we investigate document plausibility and the associated findability bias, providing strategies to improve retrieval robustness and diversity. Finally, we explore two emerging research directions: introducing span-copying mechanisms to enhance LLM efficiency and reduce hallucinations and designing fine-grained retrieval models combining LLM supervision with lightweight, interpretable retrieval architectures. These efforts collectively advance multimodal, reliable, and efficient FIR systems suitable for real-world conversational applications.</p>		

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AP	Average Precision
DM	Dialogue Manager
FIR	Factual Information Retrieval
IR	Information Retrieval
LLM	Large Language Model
MAP	Mean Average Precision
MHFA	Multi-head Factorized Attentive Pooling
MRR	Mean Reciprocal Rank
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NQ	Natural Questions
OOB	Out-of-the-box
PR	Proprietary data
QA	Question Answering
R@K	Recall@K
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
SLU	Spoken Language Understanding
SOTA	State-of-the-art
SSL	Self-Supervised Learning
ST	Sentence Transform

1 Executive Summary

This report summarizes research and experimental efforts related to WP2, Task 2 that is focused on Factual information retrieval (FIR) with conversational queries. We also discuss open research questions related to FIR such as increasing LLM efficiency, decreasing LLM hallucinations, identifying bias and semi-automatically creating relevant training and benchmark datasets that support FIR with speech queries.

In chapter 4, we are building on top of the results of T2.1 (reported in D2.1), where we developed a pipeline for processing speech conversational data by interconnecting state-of-the-art speech encoders with a LLM pre-trained on textual data. We followed the approach from D2.1 and developed a similar methodology that will enable the rapid reuse of existing text-based FIR systems to adapt them to directly handle conversational speech data. We have opted to develop our initial system presenting the methodology on a widely used state-of-the-art text BGE-M3 retrieval model which employs a versatile multilingual text embedding model targeting retrieval across over 100 languages. We present two different strategies of aligning speech conversational data into FIR framework where we either align the output of the text and speech embedding or we simply align the speech input space towards the input of text encoder in a similar way as we did for LLMs. The latter approach has achieved better results, and we see this approach as a promising direction to directly using speech queries in FIR and close the gap between FIR on text hypothesis obtained from ASR. Note that in both cases, we keep the original FIR system frozen which enables its use with text as it was originally developed with speech input which promotes multi-modality and is in line with **KR2** (Multimodality) in **Objective1** (*Advanced SLU technologies for safety-critical applications*).

To support future research on unconstrained conversational data we also developed a methodology for creating a multi-modal question answering dataset from public podcasts. The methodology is described in chapter 3 and unlike HeySQUAD (Wu, 2024) which contains spoken Wikipedia articles, and which was used in our initial experiments, our dataset relies exclusively on complete natural questions and answers extracted from authentic and organic conversations. We intend to use it to train and evaluate FIR systems that are robust to the variability and disfluencies present in spontaneous speech. As truly conversational, free-to use large-scale datasets for FIR system development are very scarce, we see the effort that we put into the dataset creation pipeline to be in line with **KR8** (Reliability/trust of generic LLMs) in **Objective 3** (*Enhanced conversational agents toward un-biased and trustworthy dialogues with end-users*). Project partners or other researchers can take the recipes and pre-trained baseline models from our GitHub repository and use it as a template for further development or benchmarking. Furthermore, in chapter 5, we report on our continued efforts for automatic dataset creation and provide updated results and analysis with the pipeline for synthetic data generation based on Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) that we introduced in D2.1 further strengthening the contribution to **KR5** (Contextualization/grounding of LLMs to real-world applications) and with **KR9** (Dynamic insertion of constraints for smart home assistant and call center virtual agents, mitigating issue of hallucination) in **Objective 2** and **Objective 3** (*Enhanced conversational agents towards un-biased and trustworthy dialogues with end-users*), respectively.

In chapter 6 we continue to work towards **Objective 3** and discuss the document plausibility and a related problem of findability bias towards the plausible documents. The presence of such bias can have significant consequences to downstream applications such as conversational agents that are powered by RAG where the response quality depends on both relevance and diversity of retrieved documents. We provide the methodology for building a model for estimating document plausibility together with experimental results and insights into the bias towards easily findable documents. This is important to improve robustness and generalizability of FIR systems and applications that depend on them. Addressing this problem in the FIR-powered application will contribute to **KR10** (Mitigate by 50% the bias in deployed models).

Finally, in chapter 7, we briefly discuss two research questions that are relevant to FIR systems based on LLMs and which address the problem of hallucination, model efficiency and interpretability. The first topic under discussion is the introduction of a span copying LLM that will substantially improve inefficient and error-prone cases when the LLM repeats previously generated text. Enabling the LLM to simply identify relevant spans to copy from its history context will not only decrease computational costs and latency, which is in line with **KR4** (Sustainability of LLMs) in **Objective 1**, but will also decrease the risk of hallucination and increases the grounding towards the input, which is in line with **KR5** (Contextualization/grounding of LLMs) in **Objective 2**. In the second topic, we discuss the problem

of fine-grained information retrieval that combines large-scale, LLM-derived supervision with a lightweight, token-wise ColBERT extension. We highlight three different architectural variants of our approach that will: (i) preserve efficiency while increasing interpretability, (ii) maximize task-specific expressivity at the cost of doubled index size and (iii) preserve retrieval footprint by applying neural network transformations to the representations of top-k retrieved documents. This research promises faster, more accurate retrieval with built-in relevance explainability—reducing redundant transformer calls, lowering latency, and curbing hallucinations in downstream applications. This is again in line with **KR4** and **KR5**. As these topics are more closely aligned with T3.1, we only highlight the results, discuss their importance and relevance to FIR and we will provide full technical description in the upcoming D3.1.

2 Introduction

Conversational AI (or dialogue) systems typically employ an information retrieval (IR) component that helps in retrieving relevant documents from a knowledge base to assist the dialogue manager (DM) to respond accurately to the users' queries. IR systems built and operated on verified, trusted knowledge sources are referred to as factual-information retrieval (FIR) systems. These are different than general purpose IR systems that rely on world-wide-web as their source. Most of the research in FIR was focused on textual domain (Thakur, 2021), mainly due to the availability of resources and the ease of pre-processing knowledge sources such as Wikipedia. A few works that extended the text-based IR to speech domain relied on spoken Wikipedia content and crowd-sourced speech for queries that already existed in textual form (Shon, et al., 2023). The resulting datasets are semi-natural and sub-optimal for studying and building speech-based conversational AI systems for the following reasons: (i) the queries appear without any dialogue or conversational context and do not carry any characteristics of spontaneous speech, (ii) the knowledge sources relying on spoken Wikipedia are redundant, since the textual version already exists. Nevertheless, such datasets are important to kindle the research and development of spoken question answering (QA) and speech-based FIR systems.

In this deliverable, we present our efforts in advancing the state of research in spoken FIR and at the same time aligning with the goals of ELOQUENCE. More specifically in chapter 3, we present a methodology for systematically creating a novel multimodal FIR dataset that contains spoken queries occurring in a natural conversational context. For this purpose, we used Spotify podcasts dataset due to its permissive license and vast size. In chapter 4, we present a methodology and results for training a speech-based FIR model using knowledge distillation from state-of-the-art multilingual text-based FIR models. This approach essentially enables us to leverage any amount of paired speech-text data and any text-based FIR model. Chapter 5 presents a methodology for the construction of synthetic dialogue-based textual question-answering dataset and subsequent training of retrieval for dialogue systems. Chapter 6 discusses open questions related to FIR models, mainly focusing on identifying the biases in the FIR datasets. Here we develop a methodology and systematically study the prior bias of document relevancy (findability), i.e., how likely a document is to be relevant without observing any queries. Finally, we provide a preview of a couple of open research questions in chapter 7 that are related to interpretability of multi-vector FIR systems and techniques for reducing hallucinations. The latter topics will be discussed in detail in D3.1, however we see that these research topics clearly overlap with D2.2.

3 Conversational Podcast-driven Multi-modal FIR Dataset

3.1 Motivation and data description

FIR systems play a critical role in conversational dialogue systems, as they help ground responses in information from a knowledge base, thereby reducing the risk of misses and hallucinations. Text-based FIR systems are typically trained and evaluated on large-scale datasets of question-answer pairs, such as MSMARCO (Nguyen, 2016), HotpotQA (Yang, 2018), and Natural Questions (Kwiatkowski, 2019).

While text-based IR is extensively studied, the research in multimodal IR systems is lagging for several reasons – lack of realistic datasets, suitable models, and algorithms that efficiently use multimodal representations. Moreover, it is also important to consider multimodal FIR systems that can use both text and audio information to retrieve relevant facts to satisfy users' information needs. In the context of speech-based multimodal FIR, it is essential to consider natural speech queries that appear in real-world conversations.

To this end, we built a conversational multimodal FIR dataset based on the Spotify podcasts dataset (Clifton, 2020). The original podcasts dataset contains approximately 100,000 episodes with 60,000 hours of audio content and provides a rich source of spontaneous speech that closely resembles natural queries in conversational settings. The duration of each podcast ranges between 30 to 90 minutes.

The dataset we built considers both the original audio recordings and their corresponding automatic transcriptions, enabling the development and evaluation of retrieval systems across four modalities of search: (1) spoken queries to spoken answers, (2) spoken queries to textual answers, (3) textual queries to spoken answers and, (4) textual queries to textual answers. This comprehensive approach facilitates the training and evaluation of retrieval systems that leverage large language models (LLMs) adapted to speech via a shared representation space, as outlined in D2.1. This also enables us to quantify the error propagation caused by a cascaded pipeline involving automatic speech recognition and text-based FIR systems.

In comparison to existing speech-based FIR datasets like HeySQUAD (Wu, 2024) and NMSQA (Lin, 2022), our dataset relies exclusively on natural questions and answers extracted from authentic and organic conversations rather than relying on synthetic or crowdsourced data. This aims at building a dataset that is more representative of real-world conversational interactions and can be used to train and evaluate FIR systems that are robust to the variability and disfluencies present in spontaneous speech. Moreover, our dataset is different from the 2020/2021 TREC Podcasts Track, also based on the Spotify dataset¹, because the latter contains only textual queries formulated by the track organizers, which do not capture the cues in natural speech queries.

3.2 Architecture of the question-answer extraction pipeline

Conventional IR datasets usually consist of three primary components: a collection of documents (the units to be retrieved), a set of queries (that represent the information needs of users), and relevance judgments (that indicate which documents are relevant to which queries). The task consists of returning a ranked list of documents for each query, based on their estimated relevance to the query.

Our goal is to extend this framework by constructing an IR dataset that incorporates both spoken and textual queries and documents derived from the Spotify podcast dataset. From the podcast dataset, we aim to identify suitable queries that simulate user information needs in a dialogue context, along with answers that serve as relevant passages from a large speech database. Specifically, we seek to extract:

- High-quality queries that are:
 - Self-contained: unambiguous for someone who has not heard the rest of the conversation.

¹ <https://trecpodcasts.github.io>

- Information-seeking: asking for general factual knowledge, not details about the speakers or the conversation.
- High-quality answers that are:
 - Self-contained: providing complete information without requiring additional context.
 - Relevant: directly addressing the corresponding question.

To extract these suitable question-answer pairs, we developed a processing pipeline using 30 random podcasts as a development set. The final automated pipeline consists of the following stages:

1. **Podcast transcription:** we automatically transcribed each audio podcast using Whisper large-v3². The output is running text, not containing speaker information or timestamps.
2. **Question extraction:** For each transcript, we extracted at most one question using GPT-4o-mini³ with instructions to identify self-contained, information-seeking questions. For each podcast, we extracted at most one question, i.e., no question is extracted if the model does not identify a suitable question.
3. **Question hallucination filter:** since the question extraction model may hallucinate questions that do not appear in the transcript, we filter out questions with less than 90% string matching with the input transcript to ensure the questions appear in the original content.
4. **Question quality filter:** because the question extraction model may not always produce high-quality questions, we additionally evaluate each extracted question using GPT-4o-mini with instructions to determine if they are both self-contained and information-seeking, producing Boolean values for each criterion.
5. **Answer extraction:** for each validated question, we located the corresponding answer within the transcript using GPT-4o-mini.
6. **Answer filter:** we discard answers that appear before their corresponding questions in the transcript, or that have less than 90% string matching with the input content, or that are extremely long (over 500 words).

Figure 3-1. Automatic question-answer extraction pipeline for Spotify podcasts.

The prompts used throughout this pipeline as instructions for LLMs were developed through simple prompt engineering on the development podcast set.

Preliminary results on an independent set of 200 random podcasts showed that the pipeline was able to extract question-answer pairs from 10% of the podcasts (20 out of 200), with a precision of 50% (10 out of 20 were identified as high-quality by manual inspection).

Based on these preliminary results, we intend to run the pipeline on a subset of podcasts that will be enough to provide an adequate number of queries at a reasonable computational cost. Finally, the manual filtering step will be performed to ensure the quality of the dataset. Manual filtering consists of annotating four criteria for each

² <https://huggingface.co/openai/whisper-large-v3>

³ <https://platform.openai.com/docs/models/gpt-4o-mini>

question-answer pair: question self-containment, question information-seeking nature, answer self-containment, and answer relevance. We will only keep samples that meet all four criteria in the final dataset.

Using the final set of validated question-answer pairs, we are building a conventional text IR dataset with the following components:

- Queries: the extracted questions
- Documents: passages of 100 words with 50-word overlap between each other, extracted from the podcasts' transcripts. Importantly, we remove the query strings within these passages to prevent trivial matching.
- Relevance judgments: established based on word overlap between the answers and the document passages. For example, if a passage contains the full answer, it is marked with a relevance of 1.0; if it contains half of the answer words, it is marked with a relevance of 0.5; and so on.

The resulting IR task requires systems to identify relevant passages for a given question within the entire database of passages across all podcasts. Examples of question-answer pairs extracted by the pipeline are shown in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1. Question-answer examples from the built Spotify FIR dataset

Question	Answer
how can I become better at math	what I tell them is pretty simple. You just have to practice. You have to study more and you have to practice, but you have to practice. And I emphasize and practice because math is not like other classes that you sit down and you study for math is not science you know for science classes literally you can sit down and memorize stuff and you'll do well in the exam but not with math [... truncated]
what are externalities	externalities are the effects that producing or consuming goods have on other third parties or society as a whole. Buyers or producers do not consider externalities when making decisions, and this can lead to market failure because goods or services can be under or over consumed
Why are people paying so much for dot-com addresses when there are plenty of other options out there, like .biz, .io, or even .pizza	One, and this surprised me, is that people do still type in words for things they want, followed by a dot-com. Not a lot of people, but with internet use growing every year, it adds up. For instance, every day, a thousand people type in ass.com, and each time they do, Rick makes a few cents. If you do the quick math, that's \$10,000 a year. And remember, he owns thousands of dot-coms. And these days, [... truncated]

To evaluate retrieval performance, we consider use two standard metrics, Recall@k and NDCG@k, which for a given query are defined as:

$$\text{Recall@k} = \frac{\text{hits@k}}{\min(R, k)}$$

$$\text{NDCG@k} = \frac{\text{DCG@k}}{\text{IDCG@k}}$$

where hits@k is the number of relevant documents retrieved in the top k results, R is the total number of relevant documents for the query, DCG@k is the discounted cumulative gain at k, and IDCG@k is the ideal discounted cumulative gain at k. DCG@k is defined as:

$$\text{DCG@k} = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{2^{\text{rel}_i} - 1}{\log_2(i + 1)}$$

where rel_i is the relevance (real number from 0 to 1) of the document at rank i, and IDCG@k is the DCG@k when the results are sorted by relevance, i.e., the ideal ranking.

To measure performance in the complete dataset, both metrics are averaged across all queries.

3.3 Aligning textual transcripts to timestamps in podcast audio

A crucial step in preparing data for multimodal FIR training involves accurately aligning textual transcripts with their corresponding segments within the audio. This alignment provides the model with the necessary grounding to understand when specific information is spoken, enabling it to answer questions related to specific moments in the audio. Without precise temporal alignment, the model might struggle to connect the textual content to the correct auditory context, hindering its ability to perform accurate QA.

Several methods can be employed for this alignment, ranging from manual annotation to automated techniques. Manual approach, where human annotators listen to the audio and manually mark the start and end timestamps for each word or phrase in the transcription is unsuitable because amount of data. Hence, we employed an automated method named forced alignment.

Force alignment is a specialized technique within automatic speech recognition (ASR) that focuses on precisely aligning a provided text transcript with its corresponding audio recording at predefined unit, frequently as phone, token or word level. Unlike standard ASR, where the system’s goal is to transcribe unknown speech, forced alignment operates under the assumption that the transcript is already known and correct (or at least very close to correct). The primary task then becomes determining the exact start and end times of each acoustic unit.

In our case, the Spotify podcasts dataset does not contain manual text transcription with timestamps. To obtain transcripts of audio podcasts we used the Whisper large v3 ASR model (Radford, et al., 2022) developed by OpenAI. It is a transformer-based encoder-decoder model trained on a massive and diverse dataset of 680,000 hours of labeled audio data. While existing inference using HuggingFace’s transformers library allows for generating transcripts with the timestamps, the resulting segments are split based on voice activity character rather than semantics at the sentence level. Therefore, we transcribed the podcast episodes as one single continuous transcription without explicit timestamps.

Figure 3-2: Process of forced alignment

Those transcriptions without timestamps were then processed by NeMo forced aligner (NFA)⁴. NFA uses connectionist temporal classification (CTC)-based ASR models. For every speech frame (time-step), the model outputs a probability distribution over the output vocabulary, which in the whole can be seen as matrix. This matrix represents, for each time step, the likelihood of each symbol (or blank) being spoken. The first step is conversion of transcription into a sequence of tokens representation that the model understands. Internally, we construct a graph of valid CTC paths for the given transcript. This representation is used as a fixed target, meaning we don't predict it, instead we force the model to align to it. Using the CTC output from model and the token graph, NFA uses a modified version of the Viterbi algorithm (best-path decoding). This finds the most likely path through time and provides token-level alignments with timestamps. These alignments are then grouped to word-level and subsequently to sentence-level alignments.

Once alignments are done, the data is formatted appropriately for audio QA training. A sample structure is given below:

```
[
  {
    "audio_filepath": "/path/to/audio segment 1.wav",
    "transcript": "This is the first segment of the audio.",
    "start_time": 1.50,
    "end_time": 5.25,
    "questions": [
      {"question": "What is your name?", "answer": "Adam."},
      {"question": "When does this segment end?", "answer": "5.25 seconds"}
    ]
  },
  {
    "audio_filepath": "/path/to/audio_segment_2.wav",
    "transcript": "Here's a question and its answer.",
    "start_time": 6.00,
    "end_time": 9.10,
    "questions": [
      {"question": "What is her name?", "answer": "Eve."},
    ]
  },
  // ... more segments
]
```

3.4 Summary and Future Directions

In this chapter, we presented our semi-automatic methodology for building a **Conversational Podcast-driven Multimodal FIR Dataset**, leveraging public podcast data to mine **authentic question-answer pairs**. Our approach integrates automatic transcription, language model-assisted question and answer extraction, strict filtering mechanisms, and forced alignment techniques to link textual and audio modalities at a fine-grained level.

By grounding the retrieval task in genuine conversational speech, rather than synthetic or crowdsourced queries, our dataset will establish a new benchmark for multimodal fact-based information retrieval (FIR). This benchmark supports speech-to-speech and speech-to-text retrieval tasks, better reflecting the variability and richness of real-

⁴ https://github.com/NVIDIA/NeMo/tree/main/tools/nemo_forced_aligner

world dialogue. In doing so, it enhances both reliability and trustworthiness of FIR systems (contributing to **KR8: Trustworthiness**), by providing a robust testbed that is more representative of natural user interactions.

Compared to prior efforts that either rely on text-only data or synthetic speech constructions, our dataset preserves the spontaneous, disfluent, and context-rich nature of human conversations. Furthermore, our methodology introduces a practical pipeline that balances automation with quality assurance, enabling the scalable creation of high-fidelity multimodal retrieval corpora.

In future work, we aim to extend this methodology to address the current scarcity of high-quality conversational spoken IR datasets. In particular, we will focus on building entirely speech-native retrieval corpora, filling the gap left by existing resources that either lack conversational realism or omit audio components altogether. These new datasets will serve as testbeds for evaluating and demonstrating the performance of our multimodal retriever on truly conversational and multi-turn spoken interactions. By expanding along these lines, we seek to push forward the frontier of multimodal and conversational information retrieval research, bringing it closer to the challenges and opportunities found in real-world applications.

4 Methodology for Adapting Text FIR System to Speech Queries

In this chapter, we describe the proposed methodology for adapting information retrieval systems to operate on speech queries. This work is an important steppingstone for establishing full end-to-end speech-to-speech information retrieval systems, which will be the subject of future work in WP2.

The aim of this work is to explore training retrieval systems that could operate on speech inputs, either in the query space, the document space, or potentially both. While opting for a standard cascaded approach – utilizing an ASR model to first transcribe the contents of a given speech query/document and subsequently encoding the ASR hypothesis using a standard text-based embedding model – is the quick, simple, and obvious solution. The cascaded approach has, however, some drawbacks.

First, there is inherent latency, as the ASR hypothesis must first be fully decoded before it can be tokenized and embedded using the text retrieval model. Second, as was the case and motivation for exploring fully end-to-end connector-based speech encoder-connector-LLM models for dialogue state tracking in D2.1, there is inherent risk for error propagation stemming from the speech representation discretization and committing to the final text representation of the ASR hypothesis during the decoding process. Third, and perhaps most importantly, adapting a speech encoder model for retrieval purposes is attractive as the said speech encoder can be the very same one used for other parts of the final dialogue system. For example, once the user provides a speech prompt, the utterance is only embedded using the speech encoder once. The output speech embedding sequence can then be processed by different connector-based downstream models. One of these models can be the retrieval model, which would, at virtually no extra latency cost (no decoding step), embed the input utterance and retrieve relevant documents for further processing by other downstream models. Then, the same speech embedding sequence can be used as input to the final dialogue LLM alongside the retrieved documents to perform whatever actions are necessary to resolve the user's query.

In this work, we take inspiration of two recent works (Min, et al., 2025) (Sun, et al., 2025) that attempt to utilize existing text retrieval models and either use them as teacher models in order to distill the output embedding space of the retrieval model into a different model that operates on sequences of speech embeddings instead of text tokens, or simply attempt to adapt the existing text embedding models to behave similarly on both text and speech inputs. The following sections describe the work and experiments that have been done until now and pose some prospects for future improvements and work.

4.1 Text-based baseline retrieval model

As the first step, it is necessary to choose a suitable standard text embedding model to serve as a reference model and the base retrieval model for further experiments. For this purpose, we adopt the M3 model from BGE-M3⁵. *M3-Embedding* (Chen, et al., 2024) is a versatile multilingual encoder-only text embedding model designed for information retrieval across over 100 languages. It uniquely supports three core retrieval paradigms – dense, sparse, and multi-vector retrieval – within a unified architecture, and can process inputs ranging from short queries to documents up to 8192 tokens. Its training leverages a novel self-knowledge distillation technique that integrates signals from different retrieval methods, improving embedding quality. The model achieves state-of-the-art (Chen, et al., 2024) performance on multilingual, cross-lingual, and long-document retrieval benchmarks.

Though considerably smaller (568M parameters) compared to other state-of-the-art LLM-based embedding models (NV-Embed-v2 – Mistral-based, 7B parameters), it serves as a reasonable baseline for our experiments regarding adapting text IR systems to speech queries. The methodology presented in the following sections should be easily extensible and adoptable for virtually any SOTA retrieval system, as the presented final connector-based paradigm

⁵ <https://huggingface.co/BAAI/bge-m3>

is very similar to the connector-based speech-LLMs presented in D2.1 for ASR and dialogue state tracking, only with a different training objective.

In our experiments, the M3 model is used as a teacher model for our speech-based models. Therefore, for both training and evaluation, we precompute the dense embedding vector representations for all training and evaluation inputs and use them either as knowledge distillation targets for our speech model, or as the document targets when evaluating the speech-based models for retrieval on question-answering data, as described in the next section.

4.2 Architecture of the FIR system with speech input

We explore two distinct approaches to training a speech-based embedding model for information retrieval. Both approaches are based on knowledge distillation with respect to the reference M3 text retrieval model, and the speech-based model is trained to model some part of the M3 model’s representation space. We refer to the two approaches as follows:

- a) Pooler-based,
- b) Connector-based.

The objective function used for both architectures is the same and is computed on the reference M3 text embedding of a given utterance and the output embedding of the student speech-based model:

$$L_{KD} = \alpha L_{MSE} + (1 - \alpha) L_{cos}$$

Here, L_{MSE} is the standard mean-squared error loss between each pooled speech embedding and its corresponding M3 text embedding ground truth, and L_{cos} is a contrastive cosine-similarity-based loss defined as follows:

$$L_{cos_i} = -\log\left(\frac{\exp(\mathbf{s}_i^T \mathbf{t}_i / \tau)}{\exp(\mathbf{s}_i^T \mathbf{t}_i / \tau) + \sum_{j \in N_i} \exp(\mathbf{s}_i^T \mathbf{t}_j / \tau)}\right)$$

Here, \mathbf{s}_i and \mathbf{t}_i are the output speech and text embedding vectors, respectively (positive pair), both being L2-normalized so that their dot product equates to cosine similarity. N_i is a sampled set of in-batch negative text embedding examples \mathbf{t}_j with respect to the positive index i , τ is the temperature hyperparameter. In our experiments, we set $\tau = 0.07$, and the number of negative examples per batch to 20.

Both loss functions are weighted with a factor α , which we find generally advantageous when it is less than 1.0, because minimizing only the Mean Squared Error (MSE) does not provide a sufficiently robust objective for training. For all presented experiments, we set $\alpha = 0.7$.

4.2.1 Pooler-based speech FIR system

The pooler-based model serves also as a baseline for our speech-retrieval experiments, and was inspired by the work conducted in (Sun, et al., 2025). The model is depicted in Figure 4-1 and encompasses training a pooling network on top of a frozen speech encoder. The speech encoder output speech embedding sequence $\mathbf{S}^{N_s \times D_s}$ of length N_s and dimensionality D_s is first downsampled by a factor F along the time dimension. The downsampling concatenates F neighbouring speech embeddings along the channel dimension, resulting in a F -times shorter sequence \mathbf{S}' of length N_s/F and dimensionality FD_s . \mathbf{S}' is subsequently projected by a linear layer to the dimensionality D_p of the pooler network.

The pooler network architecture is either a simple feed-forward layer, or a transformer encoder. In our experiments, we typically use a 2-layer transformer with a hidden size of 1024 (same as the dense embedding dimensionality of the M3 teacher model), 8 attention heads and the intermediate feed-forward layer size of 2048, totaling at around 20M parameters.

Lastly, the pooler output embedding sequence needs to be summarized into a single embedding vector. We experiment with three different types of pooling: mean pooling, simple attention-based pooling, and the multi-head factorized attention pooling, which has previously been successfully used for pooling speech representations to obtain speaker embedding vectors suitable for verification (Peng, et al., 2025).

Figure 4-1 Architecture of the pooler-based speech retrieval model.

4.2.2 Connector-based speech FIR system

As depicted in Figure 4-2 the connector based architecture closely resembles the architecture of the aligned speech LLMs from D2.1, and similar retrieval model adaptation methodology was presented in (Min, et al., 2025). The difference to the pooler-based model is that instead of directly modelling the M3 output representation space, the connector module is used to instead project the speech embeddings obtained from a frozen speech encoder into the input embedding space of the M3 model. Since the output dense text embedding representation is obtained for the transformed output representation of the CLS token, the same operation is performed in the connector scenario. However, instead of supplying the M3 model with text tokens, the connector output embeddings are injected past the word embedding layer of the M3 encoder. This allows for taking advantage of all the knowledge the M3 model had acquired during training without having to resort to crude approximations of the output dense embedding space, assuming that the connector module can appropriately learn to transform the speech embeddings so that the output M3 embedding is as close as possible to the ground truth text-only counterparts.

The architecture of the connector is like the pooler network – the same stacking/projection down sampling is first applied to the speech embedding sequence, and the down sampled embeddings are projected to the dimensionality of the connector (which we set to be the same as the hidden size of the M3 encoder – 1024). The connector itself is, again, a 2-layer transformer encoder with 8 attention heads and an intermediate feed-forward layer size of 2048. In this scheme, both the speech encoder and the M3 encoder are kept frozen, and only the connector parameters are trained.

Figure 4-2 Architecture of the connector-based speech retrieval model.

Even though M3 is an encoder-only model, this connector-based architecture is extensible to virtually any embedding model. In future work, we plan to extend this methodology to larger, LLM-based embedding models such as NV-Embed-v2, which offer state-of-the-art multilingual retrieval performance.

4.3 Experimental results

4.3.1 Training and evaluation datasets

Both architectures are trained using general speech recognition data – specifically the English subset of Mozilla Common Voice 15 (Ardila, et al., 2020). Since the speech models are not trained for retrieval directly, the general nature of datasets like Common Voice will help explore a wide variety of utterances in terms of their semantic meaning and therefore properly align the speech embedding representations to their text counterparts.

The dataset used to evaluate the trained models is SLUE-SQA-5 from SLUE Phase-2 (Shon, et al., 2023). SLUE-SQA-5 is a new spoken question answering (QA) dataset built to address the lack of large-scale, realistic human speech in previous English spoken QA datasets. It sources text questions from five major QA datasets (SQuAD, NQ, TriviaQA, WebQuestions, TREC), and collects spoken versions of these questions via Amazon Mechanical Turk. Instead of recording long spoken documents, relevant audio documents are retrieved from the Spoken Wikipedia corpus. The dataset includes fine-tune, dev, test, and a manually verified test split, all with real speech data. The train set consists of 244 hours of speech data, the dev, test, and verified test sets contain 21, 25, and 4 hours of speech data, respectively.

4.3.2 Evaluation metrics

We evaluate our models using two metrics: Hit@K and MRR@K, as our evaluation dataset has only one relevant document for each individual query. Hit@K (essentially Recall@K) is the proportion of queries for which the correct document is found in the top-K retrieved results:

$$\text{Hit@K} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N 1\{\text{rank}_i \leq K\}$$

Here, $1\{\cdot\}$ is an indicator function, rank_i is the rank position of the correct document for query i , and N is the total number of queries. MRR@K (Mean Reciprocal Rank @K) averages the reciprocal rank of the correct document across queries, but only if it's in the top-K. If it's not, the reciprocal rank is 0:

$$\text{MRR@K} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\text{rank}_i} & \text{if } \text{rank}_i \leq K \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

4.3.3 Experiments

For all experiments, we use the Whisper (Radford, et al., 2022) family of speech recognition models as our speech encoders. Namely we mostly take advantage of the English version of Whisper-small as our baseline speech encoder, which has a hidden size of 768. We additionally repeat some experiments with Whisper-large-v3 to better assess the scaling of the trained models. Two main sets of experiments are run: one with the pooler-based approach and one with the connector-based approach (further also referred to as the ‘alignment’ approach).

For the pooler experiments, two base pooler network configurations are used. The first is a simple linear layer projecting the down sampled embedding to the 1024-dimensional M3 embedding space, and the second is a 2-layer transformer with a hidden size of 1024, 8 attention head, and 2048 intermediate hidden layer dimension.

On top of each pooler network, we experiment with all the three pooling methods (mean, attention-based, MHFA). For MHFA, 8 attention heads are used, and the compression dimension is set to be 512. The MHFA adds ~5M parameters to the model.

For the connector experiments, the connector is the same 2-layer transformer as used for the pooler, totaling at around 21M (or 24M when used in conjunction with Whisper-large) parameters. Both the pooler and the connector setups use the same stacking down sampling as described in Section 4.2.1 with a subsampling factor of 6 and followed by a linear down projection to the pooler/connector dimensionality.

All training runs use a batch size of 192, 20 in-batch negative examples for the contrastive cosine loss, alpha for the MSE/cosine loss 0.7, and a learning rate of 1e-4. The training on Common Voice is run for at most 15000 steps, 100 warmup steps and an evaluation is run every 400 steps. Early stopping with patience of 3 evaluation cycles is employed to avoid overfitting. The results when evaluated for single document retrieval on the SLUE-SQA-5 combined test and verified test splits are reported in Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-4. In the figures, the ground truth text M3 retrieval is denoted as ‘text_gt’, M3 performance when using the ASR hypotheses from Whisper-small or Whisper-large are denoted as ‘text_asr_wsm’ or ‘text_asr_wlv3’, respectively. We report the WER of both Whisper models on the questions in the test sets of SQA-5 in Table 4-1. The pooler-based models are prefixed either with ‘linear’ or ‘tr’, depending on whether the pooler is a linear layer or a transformer. The pooling methods are denoted as ‘mean’, ‘attn’, or ‘mhfa’. The connector-based models are denoted as ‘aligned’.

Table 4-1 WER performance of the Whisper models on the questions of the SLUE-SQA-5 test sets.

Model	SLUE-SQA-5 test WER [%]	SLUE-SQA-5 verified-test WER [%]
Whisper-small.en	7.4	6.8
Whisper-large-v3	5.3	4.8

The pooler models with only a linear layer generally do not perform well compared to the transformer ones. However, some performance increase can be gained by using a better pooling method – mean pooling of the pooler output treats all elements in the sequence uniformly and is unable to reliably extract any relevant information and distill it into the final embedding vector. The attention pooling and MHFA on top of the linear pooler perform the same, indicating that there is a definite hard limit to the ability of modelling the M3 embedding space for these linear poolers.

Interestingly, all three models with a transformer pooler perform similarly, regardless of the chosen pooling method. The improvement over the linear poolers is significant, though the performance is still rather lackluster compared to the text baselines. Here, even though the MHFA adds about 5M parameters on top of the transformer pooler, the performance gain from this is negligible, indicating that once the pooler has some non-trivial amount of expressive capability, it becomes more and more difficult to improve the approximation of the M3 embedding space. Though improvements might still be gained by significantly diversifying the training data, using a more capable speech encoder or simply a much bigger pooling model (or incidentally, fine-tuning for the retrieval task after the fact), these experiments in general indicate that pooler-based distillation of a text embedding model is not the optimal course to take when adapting for speech inputs.

On the other hand, the aligned connector-based models outperform the pooler-based models even in the base configuration (indicated as ‘aligned’ in Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-4). Though the model requires more compute for both training and inference, as the connector outputs must be passed through the whole frozen M3 model, the results are much more promising and closer to the text baselines.

Figure 4-3 Hit@K (Recall@K) performance comparison of the M3 model and different speech-adapted retrieval models on SLUE-SQA-5.

In D2.1, we reported on the proclivity of the connector-based approaches to overfit to the domain of the training speech data and their inability to properly generalize to new speech data domains. Based on this, we take the model checkpoint produced for the ‘aligned’ run and subsequently use the SLUE-SQA-5 dataset, on which we evaluate, to further fine-tune the checkpoint on the train set to measure the effects proper target speech data domain adaptation would have. The resulting model, denoted as ‘aligned_sqa_ft’ further outperforms the base ‘aligned’ checkpoint and gets even closer to the text baselines, though still not quite matching their performance.

We repeat the alignment experiments also with Whisper-large-v3, keeping the training setup and configuration the same. The ‘aligned_wlv3’ base model trained on Common Voice already matches the Whisper-small-based ‘aligned_sqa_ft’ model in performance. Further fine-tuning on SQA-5 yields yet another increase above all other speech-based retrieval models presented in these experiments, though still coming short of the text-based baselines, even if by a small margin.

Figure 4-4 MRR@K performance comparison of the M3 model and different speech-adapted retrieval models on SLUE-SQA-5.

Using a better model for ASR (such as Whisper-large-v3, ‘asr_hyp_wlv3’) overtakes the ‘asr_hyp’ and moves closer to the ground truth text M3 performance still. However, an even bigger improvement is observed in the aligned scenario, as fine-tuning on the target data domain essentially yields partial fine-tuning effects for of the whole model on that domain (Sedláček, Kesiraju, Polok, & Černocký, 2024), as was also discussed for the connector models in D2.1. Additionally, the speech representations from Whisper large seem to simply be of much better quality, as is demonstrated by the matching performance of the ‘aligned_sqa_ft’ (fine-tuned on SQA-5) and ‘aligned_wlv3’ (only trained on Common Voice) models.

Training on more data domains has the most potential for improving the final retrieval performance compared to the experiments presented here. More experiments will be conducted in this regard in the future, focusing on further improving the performance of the aligned models and getting them closer to the text baselines. Furthermore, we will focus also on modern LLM-based embedding models such as NV-Embed-v2, which already pose a step-up in performance compared to M3 due to their size. In those scenarios, it might not be necessary to fully match the performance of the text retriever itself, as the absolute performance gained from using a more capable embedding model will overshadow the discrepancy between the end-to-end speech-based aligned model and the cascaded ASR-to-LLM retriever, mainly due to also having much lower latency as no ASR decoding has to be performed in the aligned scenario.

Lastly,

Figure

4-3

and

Figure 4-4 also shows two speech-to-speech (‘s2s_wlv3’, ‘s3s_wsm’) experiments, where we use the best two aligned models for the same task, but this time also encode the documents in the SQA-5 dataset, thus performing speech-to-speech retrieval. The performance of both models in this regard is not nearly as good as in the speech-to-text scenario and will require further investigation in future work. We hypothesize that the main reason might be the different speech domain of the documents compared to the queries/questions as well as that the documents typically contain much longer sections of text compared queries (which the models are fine-tuned on), leading to further domain mismatch.

4.3.4 Summary and future directions

In this chapter, we presented a methodology and experimental results for training a speech-based retrieval via knowledge distillation from state-of-the-art multilingual text-based retrieval model. Our experiments on SLUE-SQA-5 dataset based on spoken Wikipedia have shown that our speech-based model yielded competitive results as compared to a cascaded pipeline of ASR and text-based retrieval. We plan to continue the work in this promising direction in the following directions: (1) extend the knowledge distillation using multilingual datasets, performing experiments with large multilingual embedding models, and (2) task-specific training, i.e. including retrieval-based objectives along with knowledge distillation. Finally, we aim to quantify the effect of errors caused by the ASR model when using a cascaded pipeline. Our pre-trained models and code will be made available on the ELOQUENCE GitHub repository.

5 Building Open-Retrieval Conversational Question Answering Systems by Generating Synthetic Data and Decontextualizing User Questions

5.1 Motivation

Large Language Models (LLMs) are increasingly using Information Retrieval (IR) and Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) to access external knowledge and reduce hallucinations, particularly in conversational applications ranging from commercial chatbots to government systems. In conversational question answering (ConvQA), systems must account for dialog context when retrieving information, as simply using the last user question often fails due to conversational phenomena like co-references (Qu, 2019) and ellipsis (Choi, 2018). Current ConvQA datasets typically cover broad domains rather than specific industry use cases, creating challenges for developing domain-specific applications where annotated dialog data is scarce. To address these limitations, we build upon the work reported in D2.1 by proposing a more compact pipeline specifically tailored for generating synthetic dialogs grounded in domain-specific documents, demonstrating how these synthetic conversations can effectively train lightweight question rewriters that work with existing retrieval systems.

5.2 The pipeline

Our pipeline includes two main steps as depicted in Figure 5-1. We experiment with Omilia (proprietary) data (1036 documents) and the open-source (public) dataset Doc2Dial (Song Feng H. W., 2020), a collection of 488 documents regarding industrial data along with QA oriented document-grounded dialogs.

Figure 5-1 The proposed synthetic dialog generation pipeline.

Pipeline – Step 1: Firstly, we prompt an LLM (Claude 3.5), henceforth Dialog-LLM, to extract information from the documents as standalone sentences stating a single fact, called propositions (Tong Chen, 2024). In particular, we require each proposition to be a stand-alone simple sentence (e.g. no compound sentences, no anaphora, no ellipsis) expressing information from a document. Further, we require each proposition to convey information important enough to be requested by a user question. Following this approach, we instruct the LLM to split compound sentences into simple ones, separate information into standalone sentences and decontextualize them to remove references from one proposition to another. We extract the embeddings of the propositions using an out-of-the-box (OOB) Sentence Transform (ST) and store both the propositions themselves and their embeddings in separate data stores to be retrieved by either a sparse (using BM25) or a dense (using the same ST) retriever respectively. In total, we get 11566 propositions (out of 20520 sentences) from the Omilia data and 14443 propositions (out of 17197 sentences) from Doc2Dial.

Pipeline – Step 2: In the second step we generate synthetic dialogs from a set of propositions, again by prompting the same LLM. This is done using 3 separate prompts.

- Prompt 2.1: Prompt 2.1 instructs Dialog-LLM to generate a dialog between a user and a system, grounded on a set of propositions (maintaining the order they were created). Each set contains 30 propositions which allows us to cover a wider range of possible questions while also restricting the subject to a few documents. For this

sub-step, we specifically instruct the model to generate self-contained questions that include all the necessary information from the dialog context.

- Prompt 2.2: With prompt 2.2, we instruct the same LLM to create contextualized versions of the user questions, considering the dialog context. If the question introduces information that is not present in the context, the output of the model is the same. If this is not the case, the model is instructed to introduce dialog phenomena such as coreference and ellipsis. As a result, there are two versions of each user question: the contextualized version and the decontextualized one, along with the system response. We use these two versions to train and compare three models (T5, Mamba and GPT2) for query rewriting (the task of decontextualization). The number of parameters per model is 250M, 370M and 350M respectively. Note that we generate rewrites regardless of the case. For instance, if a query is already decontextualized (e.g. the first turn), the rewriter model ideally will generate the same query. A snippet of a synthetic dialog is depicted in Figure 5-2. A case of coreference and omission is marked with red and blue respectively.
- Prompt 2.3: Finally, prompt 2.3 instructs the Dialog-LLM to generate, for each answer-question pair, the propositions that it used for their generation. Each turn of every dialog now contains two versions of the user query (with and without rewriting), the system response and the corresponding propositions. The LLM is also instructed to generate either the token 'accepted' or 'not_accepted' for each dialog pair, signifying whether the pair is indeed grounded in the selected propositions or not. We remove pairs marked as 'not_accepted' and replace each subsequent user question with its decontextualized version, to avoid referring to a removed pair.

```

Turn 2
<user> : How can I show it?
<rewritten_user> : How can I show the Associate Call/SMS Log with Person Account section?
<system> : To show the Associate Call/SMS Log with Person Account section, the user is required to be a partner
accepted 1

Turn 3
<user> : Where can I find the Organization ID?
<rewritten_user> : Where can I find the Salesforce.com Organization ID?
<system> : The user can find the 'Salesforce.com Organization ID' field in Settings>Company Information.
accepted 1

```

Figure 5-2 Snippet of a synthetic dialogue from a set of propositions.

5.3 The importance of using propositions instead of plain documents for dialog generation

To verify the superiority of using propositions to generate dialogs instead of chunks of sentences (extracted directly from the documents) we first evaluate the relevance between the user questions and the ground truth passages (the propositions on which the question is grounded) as well as the coherence of the generated dialogs. To measure the relevance (in a range between 0 and 1) we leverage QRELScore (Xiaoqiang Wang, 2022), which is based on BERT and GPT2 (fine-tuned for the task on a large set of question/passage pairs) that jointly express the relevance between a single dialog question and its corresponding ground truth passage. Additionally, we leverage QUANTIDCE (Zheng Ye, 2021) to evaluate the coherence of the dialogs generated by either propositions or sentences (in a range between 1 and 5). For QRELScore we measure the relevance of both contextualized (co) and decontextualized (de) user utterances. We only measure QUANTIDCE for contextualized utterances.

Table 5-1 Relevance (QRELScore) and Coherence (QUANTIDCE) results for synthetic dialogs generated through propositions (Prop) or sentences (Sent) using proprietary (PR) and public documents (PU). (co): contextualized questions, (de): decontextualized questions.

Docs		QRELScore (co)	QRELScore (de)	QUANTIDCE (co)
PR	Prop	0.36	0.41	3.16
	Sent	0.25	0.27	3.18
PU	Prop	0.33	0.36	3.08
	Sent	0.33	0.35	3.14

From the results in Table 5-1 we conclude that dialogs based on propositions and sentences are overall on par, so we turn to a retrieval task to define the superior approach. We treat propositions and sentences in exactly the same manner when using our pipeline and applying IR.

5.4 Information retrieval on synthetic data

To enhance the robustness of our experimental evaluation and to adhere to a more robust and statistically significant approach, we implemented a 3-fold cross-validation methodology rather than relying on a single experimental run (as was the case in D2.1). By averaging performance metrics across these three iterations (viz. partitions of the data), we obtained a more reliable estimate of the pipeline's performance, reduced the variance in our results, and minimized the influence of randomness that might otherwise bias performance assessment in a single-run scenario.

As our retriever for both sentence-generated and propositions-generated dialogs, as well as for the subsequent sets of experiments, we use Reciprocal Rank Fusion (RRF) which combines the ST and BM25 passages scores as follows:

$$score_i = \frac{1}{rank_i^b + k} + \frac{1}{rank_i^d + k}$$

where $score_i$ refers to the new score assigned by RRF, i is the index of the propositions regardless of rank, b and d refer to BM25 and dense retrieval, respectively, and k is set to 60 as per usual practices.

For the evaluation we employ MAP, MRR and Recall@K as quantitative performance criteria.

Mean Average Precision (MAP) evaluates the quality of ranked retrieval results. It calculates the mean of the Average Precision (AP) scores for each query in a set of queries. AP is calculated as the average precision of each query over multiple k values (specifically the ranks where relevant documents appear). In turn, MAP is calculated as the average of AP over all queries. Higher values are better for MAP. A higher MAP indicates better overall performance of the retrieval system.

Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) evaluates any process that produces a list of possible responses to a sample of queries, ordered by probability of correctness. The reciprocal rank of a query response is the multiplicative inverse of the rank of the first correct answer. MRR is the average of the reciprocal ranks over a set of queries. Higher values are better for MRR. A higher MRR suggests that correct answers appear earlier in the ranked list of results.

Recall@K (R@K) measures the proportion of relevant items that are retrieved in the top K results. It is the ratio of the number of relevant items retrieved to the total number of relevant items in the dataset, considering only the top K results. Higher values are better for R@K. A higher R@K indicates that a larger proportion of relevant items are being retrieved within the top K results.

The results of the experimental comparison in IR between sentence-based and propositions-based dialogs are depicted in Table 5-2. For both proprietary data (PR) and Doc2Dial (PU), data propositions (prop) outperform sentences (sent), justifying the choice of propositions over (chunks of) sentences for dialog generation. For propositions of both datasets we also notice that decontextualized queries manage to improve the IR results over contextualized queries or the concatenation of the last contextualized query with the dialog history (Context) as expected; a conclusion that is far less noticeable in the case of sentence-based dialogs. Finally, in terms of the Context, we notice that the IR performance is much lower compared to the other approach, which can be justified by the fact that the dialog history may introduce additional query irrelevant information that can confuse the retriever. Based on the results presented thus far, we continue experimenting using propositions-based dialogs and excluding context due to its (justified) underwhelming performance.

Table 5-2 RRF retrieval results in synthetic dialogs generated through propositions (Prop) or sentences (Sent) using proprietary (PR) and public (DOC2DIAL) documents (PU). Context: concatenated last user question and history, Query_{co}: contextualized question only, Query_{de}: ground-truth decontextualized question only.

PR	Query	MAP	R@5	R@10	R@20
Prop	Context	0.19	0.31	0.44	0.56
	Query _{co}	0.46	0.55	0.63	0.69
	Query _{de}	0.50	0.60	0.67	0.73
Sent	Context	0.09	0.13	0.20	0.27
	Query _{co}	0.20	0.25	0.30	0.35
	Query _{de}	0.21	0.26	0.31	0.37
PU	Query	MAP	R@5	R@10	R@20
Prop	Context	0.18	0.30	0.44	0.56
	Query _{co}	0.49	0.59	0.65	0.72
	Query _{de}	0.54	0.63	0.71	0.77
Sent	Context	0.12	0.19	0.27	0.36
	Query _{co}	0.30	0.37	0.43	0.50
	Query _{de}	0.31	0.39	0.46	0.52

To highlight the potential of our synthetic data, we also fine-tune the three models described in Prompt 2.1 for query rewriting. The results are presented in Table 5-3. From the results, we conclude that all three query rewriters outperform both Context and the Query_{co} from Table 5-2. T5 being slightly ahead compared to the other 2 query rewriters, performs almost on par with the decontextualized queries from Dialog-LLM.

Table 5-3 Additional RRF retrieval results in synthetic dialogs generated via propositions, using proprietary (PR) and public (PU) documents, and the decontextualized user questions of lightweight fine-tuned rewriters as queries. Results comparable to those of Table 5-2.

	Query	MAP	R@5	R@10	R@20
PR	GPT2	0.47	0.56	0.64	0.71
	Mamba	0.48	0.57	0.64	0.71
	T5	0.49	0.57	0.65	0.72
PU	GPT2	0.51	0.60	0.67	0.74
	Mamba	0.51	0.60	0.67	0.74
	T5	0.52	0.62	0.69	0.76

Finally, we verify the quality of the generated dialogs in systems response generation. For the task we leverage an 8 billion parameter Llama 3 model (instruct version) and instruct it to generate the desired system response given the Query_{co}, Query_{de} or rewritten query using T5 (as it had the best results of the 3 rewriters) and the corresponding top-20 retrieved propositions of each query.

We evaluate the results using SacreBLEU (SBLEU), METEOR, BERTScore (BSC), and Perplexity (PL), between the generated response and the ground truth one (as generated by the Dialog-LLM). Both SacreBLEU and METEOR perform n-gram matching to determine the similarity between the generated query and the ground truth, while BERTScore leverages an LM (BERT) to compare the two sentences semantically. Finally, perplexity relies on the probability of the correct word being generated by the response generator. The results are presented in Table 5-4. For response generation we reach the same conclusion with the previous experiments. T5 rewrites outperform Query_{co} and are outperformed by Query_{de}.

Table 5-4 Response generation results in synthetic dialogs generated via propositions from proprietary (PR) and public (PU) documents, using RRF retrieval.

	Query	SBLEU	METEOR	BSC	PL
PR	Query _{co}	40.57	55.81	93.24	3.78
	T5	42.79	58.67	93.65	3.34
	Query _{de}	44.52	59.72	93.99	3.25
PU	Query _{co}	44.92	58.99	93.39	3.03
	T5	47.33	62.11	93.80	2.74
	Query _{de}	48.73	63.46	94.08	2.68

5.5 Experiments on Doc2Dial and MultiDoc2Dial test sets

Finally, we evaluate the performance of the T5 rewriter on the real test dialogs of both Doc2Dial and MultiDoc2Dial (a version of Doc2Dial where each dialog may be grounded on more than one documents) (Song Feng S. S., 2021), without fine-tuning the rewriter further. As the datasets themselves do not include ground truth decontextualized queries, we prompt Claude 3.5 to rewrite the test user queries. Moreover, we cannot evaluate the system using propositions, as no propositions are present in the Doc2Dial datasets. Instead, we retrieve passages (a concatenation of few sentences), as the granularity of the task. The results for both Doc2Dial datasets are presented in Table 5-5. Even in the case of manually generated test cases, we still reach the same conclusions in terms of query performance as was the case with the experiments regarding synthetic data.

Finally, we also experimented with response generation for the MultiDoc2Dial dataset. We use the same setup as with the experiments on synthetic data. We use Llama-8B and provide the contextualized query (directly from the MultiDoc2Dial dataset), the rewritten query using T5 or the rewritten one using Claude along with their corresponding top-20 retrieved propositions. The results are depicted in Table 5-6. We notice a considerable drop in response generation performance compared to the experiments on synthetic data, but this can be attributed to the queries of the dataset itself. Specifically, the system itself may ask the user a question (e.g., to confirm or request more information on a subject), which our setup does not consider.

Table 5-5 RRF passage retrieval results in real-world dialogs from DOC2DIAL (D2D) and MULTIDOC2DIAL (MD2D). T5/Claude: question rewritten by T5/Claude.

	Query	MAP	R@5	R@10	R@20
D2D	Query _{co}	0.17	0.26	0.34	0.40
	T5	0.21	0.31	0.41	0.48
	Claude	0.25	0.36	0.47	0.56
MD2D	Query _{co}	0.17	0.26	0.34	0.40
	T5	0.21	0.31	0.40	0.48
	Claude	0.23	0.34	0.44	0.53

Table 5-6 Response generation results in real-world dialogs from MULTIDOC2DIAL, using RRF retrieval of propositions. Responses generated by LLAMA-8B in our methods.

	Query	SBLEU	METEOR	BSC	PL
MD2D	Query _{co}	6.16	20.93	85.63	26.04
	T5	6.54	22.65	85.74	23.08
	Claude	6.52	23.34	85.47	21.75

5.6 Conditional question rewriting

In our experiments, especially for synthetic dialog generation, we noticed that most questions are not in need of rewriting. For queries that are already decontextualized (e.g., the first user utterance) our query rewriter will have to generate a copy of the input query, word by word, a process that is time consuming. Thus, we propose a conditional questions rewriting approach. We follow the same setup when fine-tuning our query rewriter, leveraging T5 once again, and only altering the training data. We append a special token before every last user utterance signifying whether the query itself requires rewriting or not, as the first token to be generated by the query rewriter. During inference, if the rewriter generates the token that signifies that the query is already decontextualized and does not require rewriting, we stop the generation process and set the input as the generated query rewrite. The performance of the conditional query rewriter is identical with the original one from Table 5-3, in synthetic data from both proprietary (Omilia) and public (Do2Dial) documents. However, the reduction in generation time is considerable. Specifically, the average generation time for proprietary dialogs is reduced from 0.19 seconds to 0.09 (53% reduction) and for public dialogs from 0.24 seconds to 0.09 (62% reduction). We inform the reader that 36% of synthetic proprietary and 27% public user questions require rewriting.

5.7 Summary

The presented novel pipeline generates synthetic annotated document-grounded dialogs, to alleviate the lack of training data in new application domains. The pipeline requires only a set of relevant domain-specific documents. We highlighted the importance of using propositions, rather than document sentences, for dialog generation, and showed experimentally that they lead to synthetic dialogs that are clearly superior in retrieval performance, and on par or superior to dialogues generated from document sentences in coherence and relevance. Using only our synthetic data, we trained light question rewriters, which allow utilizing dialog-unaware retrievers without fine-tuning them. We showed that the rewriters substantially improve performance, compared to using the original questions with or without dialog history, and that their performance is comparable to obtaining rewrites by prompting LLMs. We also introduced a joint efficient question classification/rewriter.

6 Document Plausibility Model and Its Use for FIR

6.1 Motivation

The first stage of information retrieval ("first-stage retrieval") is usually performed by dense bi-encoders that convert queries and documents into a shared embedding space. Retrieval is carried out by measuring the similarity between a query's vector and those of documents previously stored in an index and returning the top-k most similar documents. Recent state-of-the-art (SOTA) first-stage bi-encoders according to the popular MTEB benchmark⁶ include NV-Embed-v2 (Chankyu Lee, 2024), GTE-Qwen2-7B-instruct⁷, and BGE-EN-ICL (Chaofan Li, 2024).

In the zero-shot setting, these models are applied to new data without additional domain-specific fine-tuning or few-shot examples, and have shown stronger generalization capabilities than traditional sparse lexical methods like BM25 (Robertson, 2009) -- while the latter rely on exact keyword matching between queries and documents, dense bi-encoders can capture semantic similarities beyond simple keyword matching (Santhanam, 2022) (Thakur, 2021).

Dense bi-encoders are typically initialized from pre-trained language models and fine-tuned on supervised data consisting of queries paired with relevant documents. The model is trained to maximize the similarity between the embeddings of queries and their relevant documents, while minimizing the similarity between queries and non-relevant documents. Since most datasets contain only annotations for relevant documents, negative mining techniques are used to sample non-relevant documents for training (Karpukhin, 2020).

As an instance of supervised learning, it is reasonable to believe that dense retrievers' performance can be closely tied to the distribution of the training data, i.e., first-stage retrievers probably generalize better to queries and documents that are like those seen during training. This dependency can introduce biases, as the model may overfit to the prevalent topics, styles, and document formats present in the training data, but may struggle to generalize to underrepresented topics or alternative document formats. In the context of FIR, this means that when the model is deployed on queries or document collections that diverge from the training distribution, it may fail to retrieve some or all the relevant documents.

We hypothesize that this bias exists, primarily based on two key findings from previous research:

1. Document findability variance: prior work indicates that some documents are harder to "find" than others, i.e., **some documents are less likely to be retrieved by systems even if they are relevant to a given query** (Sinha, 2023).
2. Document pruning without major performance loss: recent studies have shown that a significant portion of IR collections can be pruned with only minor performance degradation. For example, a pruning approach that estimates the relevance of documents without query context was able to remove around 90% of collection content with just a small drop in performance in two datasets (Fajcik, Docekal, Ondrej, & Smrz, 2021). Other studies explored other strategies leading to similar results (Izacard, 2020). **This suggests that there is a strong prior over content judged as relevant in IR datasets, and thus, a large portion of the documents in some collections are not essential for retrieval.** Therefore, if a query is asked about these documents, will systems be able to find them?

We hypothesize that the two findings discussed above are linked. Specifically, we conjecture that SOTA dense retrievers can exhibit a bias in favor of documents that align more closely with the distribution of training data, while downgrading and failing to retrieve documents that deviate from this distribution. In other words, "plausible" documents are more findable than "implausible" ones.

These implausible documents may differ from plausible ones in various ways: they could address underrepresented topics, use alternative formats or linguistic styles, or present novel perspectives on familiar subjects. Dense retrievers may tend to prioritize plausible passages that resemble those explicitly labeled as ground truth, potentially overlooking implausible documents that are equally relevant but less conventional. This effect may be

⁶ <https://huggingface.co/spaces/mteb/leaderboard>

⁷ <https://huggingface.co/Alibaba-NLP/gte-Qwen2-7B-instruct>

further amplified by the incompleteness of IR annotations, as typically only a subset of the truly relevant documents is labeled as such.

This phenomenon can have significant consequences in conversational agents powered by retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), where response quality depends on the relevance and diversity of retrieved documents. If retrievers favor plausible documents, RAG-generated answers may be based on non-exhaustive sources, leading to biased or unfair responses. In cases where relevant documents are highly implausible, such as when a query refers to an unlikely topic or a novel domain, the retriever may fail to retrieve any relevant documents at all. This failure can increase the likelihood of RAG systems producing unsatisfactory responses, as they must generate answers without sufficient supporting evidence.

In summary, if there is in fact a findability bias toward plausible documents, it raises concerns not only for information retrieval performance itself but also for downstream applications reliant on retrieval, such as conversational agents. Understanding this bias is crucial for improving the robustness and generalizability of FIR systems and the applications that depend on them.

6.2 Plausibility Model

We define plausibility as the probability $P(R = r|d)$, where r represents binary relevance and d represents a document. That is, we plausibility refers to the probability of a document being relevant “a priori”, i.e., without considering any particular query information. Our goal is to estimate document plausibility in SOTA dense retrievers by training a model that predicts document relevance based solely on its content. Then we can use this model to analyze the relationship between document plausibility and findability, and to assess the effect of plausibility on retrieval performance.

6.2.1 Training

We train the plausibility distribution model, $P_{\theta}(R|d)$, using the publicly available training data from BGE-EN-ICL⁸. The dataset consists of queries paired with relevant documents sourced from various IR datasets, together with hard negatives mined from the collections. Because we want to estimate the *a priori* plausibility of documents, we do not use queries for training. Besides document retrieval benchmarks, the dataset includes data from other tasks, like classification or clustering. We do not exclude these for training because we want to capture the general distribution of relevant documents in the training data of SOTA retrievers, whether they come from retrieval benchmarks or other sources.

We treat plausibility estimation as a binary classification task, discriminating relevant documents from non-judged ones. We use documents labeled as relevant in the BGE-EN-ICL dataset as positives (excluding held-out documents for testing, see Section 6.2.2), and the hard negatives mined for training as negatives (see Table Table 6-1). We train a simple binary logistic regression classifier that minimizes cross-entropy loss with Stochastic gradient descent and uses document embeddings generated by BGE-EN-ICL as input features. To allow non-linear function fitting, we also include squared embeddings in input features. Since the dataset is imbalanced, we sample weights in the loss function as the inverse of the class frequencies in the training set, ensuring equal weighting for both classes. We do not use a separate validation set because the model is fairly simple and no hyperparameter tuning is required.

Table 6-1. Training data of the plausibility model.
FIR datasets tasks in bold. Details about each dataset can be found in (Chaofan Li, 2024)

Dataset	Positive samples	Negative samples
msmarco_passage	497,996	5,401,188

⁸ <https://huggingface.co/BAAI/bge-en-icl>

triviaQA	496,974	1,929,039
eli5	323,293	314,059
msmarco_document	312,589	571,563
nli	250,368	257,323
Clustering (twenty_news_groups, biorxiv_abstract, medrxiv_abstract, arxiv_title, arXiv_abstract, biorxiv_title, medrxiv_title, stack_exchangeP2P, reddit, redditP2P, stack_exchange)	102,463	661,344
hotpotqa	98,779	394,690
quora	49,477	313,198
nq	38,467	2,534,319
stack_overflow_dup_questions	19,312	339,850
squad	17,002	17,002
fiqa	12,130	24,937
scidocsrr	10,793	79,357
fever	5,230	82,984
arguana	3,353	8,276
sts	1,518	12,319
Classification (toxic_conversations, amazon_counterfactual, emotion, banking, amazon_reviews, mtop_intent, tweet_sentiment_extraction, imdb)	209	209

We refer to this binary classifier as the plausibility model. A higher score indicates that the document is more "plausible" in the sense that it is more likely to be annotated as relevant in training datasets, while a lower score suggests that the document diverges from the distribution of relevant documents.

6.2.2 Evaluation

Our plausibility model $P_{\theta}(R|d)$ aims at learning the training distribution of a SOTA retriever, with the goal of estimating the *a priori* relevance of a document according to the retriever. This is not a traditional classification task where we would assume the possibility of distinguishing between classes exists. However, we conduct an evaluation to determine whether our model can differentiate relevant documents from non-judged ones in retrieval tasks, at least better than random.

For this evaluation, we build a test set using the retrieval datasets from the BGE-EN-ICL training data in Table 6-2). We sample 15% of positive documents from each dataset, with a maximum of 2,000 documents, only considering documents that appear exclusively as positive in the data. This is because the plausibility dataset has some overlap between positive and negative documents—when training the retriever, some documents appear as both relevant to certain queries and as hard negatives for others⁹. The Arguana dataset is excluded since it lacks such positive-only documents.

The positive documents selected for evaluation are removed from the plausibility training set. As test negative samples, we select an equal number of non-judged documents from each dataset's full collection, ensuring they are not part of the BGE-EN-ICL dataset. We use the area under the ROC curve (AUROC) as an evaluation metric to assess the model's ability to detect the plausible documents under any operating point threshold (see Table 6-2).

⁹ We also tried keeping the overlapping documents, but it led to worse classification performance.

Table 6-2. Evaluation of the plausibility model on test documents.

15% of positive-only documents are selected from the BGE-EN-ICL dataset, with a cap of 2,000. An equal number of non-judged documents are sampled from each dataset collection.

Dataset	AUROC	N per class
fever	0.962	1,026
triviaQA	0.839	2,000
hotpotqa	0.813	2,000
nq	0.810	1,407
msmarco_document	0.683	2,000
fiqa	0.584	377
scidocsrr	0.545	110
quora	0.538	743
msmarco_passage	0.531	2,000
TOTAL	0.698	23,326

Overall, the model achieves an AUROC of 0.698 across all datasets, indicating a moderate ability to distinguish positive from non-judged documents—clearly above random—but with considerable variation across datasets. Performance is surprisingly strong on datasets such as FEVER (0.962), TriviaQA (0.839), and HotpotQA (0.813), while it is notably lower on ScidocsRR (0.545), Quora (0.538), and MSMARCO Passage (0.531).

Understanding these results requires further analysis, but we hypothesize that the overlap between positive and negative samples in the plausibility training data may play a role. For instance, in datasets such as FEVER, TriviaQA, and HotpotQA, the proportion of positive samples that also appear as negatives is relatively low to moderate (10.2%, 69.3%, and 24.3%, respectively). In contrast, ScidocsRR, Quora, and MSMARCO Passage have significantly higher overlap rates (97.0%, 95.0%, and 88.3%, respectively), which could contribute to the model's reduced performance in these datasets.

Although we use the BGE-EN-ICL fine-tuning dataset for plausibility training, we hypothesize our findings apply to other top retrievers. While they differ in their pre-training and fine-tuning, their overall approach is essentially similar, so we expect similar biases. Our subsequent result supports this hypothesis. We assess the hypothesis by analyzing whether plausibility affects the embedding space of LLM-based bi-encoder retrievers NV-Embed-v2 and GTE-Qwen2-7B-instruct, both top performers in the MTEB retrieval benchmark at the time of writing.

We use two large document collections: English Wikipedia paragraphs (from the English MIRACL version, (Zhang, 2023) and StackExchange answers (from the LoTTE dataset, (Santhanam, 2022)). Documents are grouped into 20 equal-length bins based on their plausibility—as estimated by our plausibility model. We then compute the average cosine similarity for 5,000 randomly sampled document pairs from each pair of bins, excluding comparisons of the same document. If plausibility had no correlation to the similarity in the embedding space, the average similarity would be close to constant across all groups, with no clear patterns or significant differences.

Our results in Figure 6-1 show that plausibility is correlated to the embedding similarity, with patterns varying between collections and models. In Wikipedia, highly plausible documents are more similar to each other and less similar to lower-plausibility ones. For NV-Embed-v2, low-plausibility documents show particularly high similarity. In the Stack Exchange corpus, patterns vary by model, but similarity is generally higher for documents with plausibility between 0.1 and 0.5. These findings suggest that plausibility is encoded in models beyond BGE-EN-ICL. Since documents with different plausibility scores tend to be in different regions of the embedding space, this could impact retrieval results.

Figure 6-1. Average cosine similarity between 5,000 random pairs of documents for each pair of plausibilities. The first plausibility bin in Stack Exchange is greyed out because it contains only 6 documents.

6.3 Analyzing Embeddings with Plausibility Model

6.3.1 Findability

Following (Sinha, 2023), we define a document's findability as the average gain across all queries for which it is relevant:

$$f@k(d) = \frac{1}{|Q_d|} \sum_{q \in Q_d} g(d, q, k)$$

where Q_d is the set of queries for which document d is relevant, and $g(d, q, k)$ is the “gain” obtained by a retriever for query q considering the top k retrieved results. Same as (Sinha, 2023), we defined gain as the reciprocal rank of d within the top k results:

$$g(d, q, k) = \frac{1}{p_q} \text{ if } p_q \leq k, \text{ else } 0$$

where p_q is d 's rank for query q . We set k to 100. For example, if a document is retrieved at rank 1, $g = 1$, at rank 2 $g = 1/2$, ..., at rank 100, $g = 1/100$, and at rank 101 or larger $g = 0$.

6.3.2 Exploring the Relationship Between Plausibility and Findability

Next, we explore the relationship between findability and plausibility of documents. Currently, we analyze only documents annotated as relevant in retrieval datasets. This is because non-relevant documents are not associated with any dataset query, making it impossible to compute a findability score for them.

For each relevant document, we compute a plausibility score using our model and calculate the findability score for multiple retrieval methods. We evaluate three dense neural retrieval models—BGE-EN-ICL, NV-Embed-v2, and gte-Qwen2-7B-instruct—and the traditional (non-neural) sparse lexical retrieval method BM25.

Our hypothesis is that document plausibility positively correlates with findability in SOTA bi-encoders, i.e., *more plausible documents should be easier to find*. And we expect any effect to be stronger for dense retrieval models, which leverage supervised relevance judgments, than for BM25, which relies solely on lexical overlap. To assess this, we first group documents into equal-length bins based on plausibility scores and compute the average plausibility and findability within each bin.

We focus only on asymmetric retrieval search datasets, which are important for conversational agents. In these cases, queries are short (e.g., questions or keywords), while documents are longer passages. Unlike symmetric tasks, swapping queries and documents doesn't make sense. We use LoTTE (Santhanam, 2022), English MIRACL (Zhang, 2023), and selected datasets from BEIR (Thakur, 2021), excluding symmetric search ones (see Table 6-3). We also exclude HotpotQA because it requires multi-hop retrieval, meaning some documents are only relevant if others are retrieved first. Therefore, not all documents are equally relevant, making it difficult to filter documents by relevance. For BEIR datasets, we only use test and development queries to ensure that no samples used for training the plausibility model or the retrieval models are included.

Table 6-3. Datasets used to assess the relationship between plausibility and findability.

Dataset	# Relevant Documents	# Queries
climate-fever (BEIR)	1,344	1,535
dbpedia-entity (BEIR)	16,182	467
Fever (BEIR)	2,892	13,332
fiqa (BEIR)	2,944	1,148
LoTTE	142,887	26,919
MIRACL	9,735	3,662
Msmarco (BEIR)	11,530	7,023
Nfcorpus (BEIR)	3,338	647
NQ (BEIR)	4,201	3,452
Scidocs (BEIR)	4,020	1,000
Scifact (BEIR)	283	300

Our results are shown in Figure 6-2. For most datasets, except for scifact and scidocs, we see a clear positive trend between findability using dense methods and plausibility (Figure 6-2). This suggests that less plausible documents are generally harder to find with dense methods. Differently, our non-neural baseline method, BM25, does not exhibit a consistent pattern. For BM25, the results vary across datasets, sometimes showing an upward trend (e.g., LoTTE), sometimes a downward trend (e.g., MIRACL), and sometimes an unclear trend (e.g., climate-fever). This supports our hypothesis that the plausibility model is learned “secretly” during retriever training (as the trend with findability is unique to dense models trained with contrastive learning).

Figure 6-2. Average plausibility (x-axis) vs. average findability (y-axis).

Documents are grouped into equal-sized plausibility bins, ranging from the dataset's minimum to maximum. Each point represents a group's average plausibility and findability across different methods. Error bars show 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Even if the plausibility-findability curves suggest a positive relationship, we want to make sure that the correlation between plausibility and findability is not driven by other factors. Specifically, we want to control for three potential confounding variables:

1. **Document length.** There is a moderate positive correlation between document length and plausibility (see Table 6-4). While this is not inherently problematic, we want to ensure that the plausibility-findability relationship depends on a deeper relation than just a word count.
2. **Relevance grade.** Some datasets have graded relevance labels (MSMARCO, DBpedia-entity, NFCorpus). Documents with higher relevance grades are easier to find as they might contain more relevant content, so we control for this factor to focus on plausibility alone.
3. **Number of “related documents”.** We define a document’s “related documents” as those relevant to the same queries. The number of related documents affects the expected findability score of relevant documents because they will tend to have lower individual reciprocal ranks. Let’s consider the example of a perfect retriever where related documents have similar plausibility scores. If a query has 10 relevant documents, their average reciprocal rank will be less than 1, even if all documents are perfectly retrieved -- whereas if a query has only one relevant document, the reciprocal rank will be 1. If plausibility correlates with the number of related documents, then it can indirectly affect findability. Therefore, we control for this factor as well.

Table 6-4. Spearman correlations between word count and plausibility in relevant documents. All values are significantly different from 0 at $\alpha=0.01$ level.

Dataset	Corr (word count, plausibility)
climate-fever	0.365
dbpedia-entity	0.282
fever	0.339
fiqa	0.136
lotte	0.181
miracl	0.18
msmarco	0.042
nfcopus	0.265
nq	0.192
scidocs	0.325
scifact	0.352

To control for these factors, we fit a linear regression model for each dataset and retrieval method, with document findability as the target variable and document plausibility, document length (word count), average document relevance grade, and the number of related documents (documents relevant for the same query) as covariates (i.e., input features). For datasets without graded relevance or with a constant number of related documents, we exclude the corresponding feature. We include the plausibility score in log scale to capture non-linear relationships. To compare across datasets and methods, we standardize the target variable to have a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. Since the findability score is averaged over queries, documents with more queries have less variance in their findability estimate. To compensate for this, we estimate the coefficients using weighted least squares, with the number of queries per document as the weights.

We analyze the magnitude and significance of the plausibility coefficient in the regression (Figure 6-3). We find that plausibility generally has a positive effect on findability across most models and datasets, except for scifact, scidocs (NV-Embed-v2), and NFCorpus (NV-Embed-v2). In other words, even when accounting for potential confounders, less plausible documents are harder to find using the dense bi-encoders. What is more, trends tend to be similar between the models considered. For BM25, the average coefficient is close to 0, showing a positive effect in some datasets (e.g., NQ), a negative effect in others (e.g., MSMARCO), and no significant effect in others (e.g., LOTTE).

Figure 6-3. Regression coefficient of $\log(\text{plausibility})$ on standardized findability.

Greyed-out points indicate coefficients that are not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 significance level. Vertical coloured bars show the average coefficient for each method. Datasets are sorted according to the average coefficient for dense models.

6.3.3 Exploring the Relationship Between Plausibility and Retrieval Performance

We now examine whether plausibility affects retrieval performance for queries with relevant documents of low plausibility. For each query, we calculate the average plausibility of its relevant documents and group the queries into bins based on this value. We then measure retrieval performance (nDCG@100) and the mean average plausibility across bins, hypothesizing that queries with lower plausibility in their relevant documents will have lower retrieval effectiveness.

We observe a clear positive relationship between average plausibility and retrieval effectiveness for dense methods across many datasets—e.g., climate-fever, DBpedia-entity, NQ (Figure 6-4). However, this effect is either weak or absent in other datasets (e.g., scidocs, MSMARCO, NFCorpus). For BM25, the trends are less consistent—sometimes even negative (e.g., MSMARCO, MIRACL, FEVER), constant (e.g., DBpedia-entity), and sometimes slightly positive (e.g., LoTTE).

To ensure the effect holds even after controlling for other factors, we conduct a regression analysis analogous to the one performed in the previous section. Here, we model nDCG@100 as a function of average document plausibility while controlling for the average document length (word count) and average relevance grade of the relevant documents. This helps confirm that the plausibility effect is not driven by these factors. As before, we standardize the target variable and use the log of average document plausibility.

Figure 6-4. Mean average plausibility (x-axis) vs. NDCG@100 (y-axis).

Queries are grouped based on the average plausibility of their relevant documents, using equal-sized bins from the dataset's minimum to maximum. Each point represents the group's mean average plausibility (the average of average plausibility across queries) and NDCG@100 for different methods. Error bars indicate 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

Figure 6-5. Regression coefficient of $\log(\text{plausibility})$ on standardized findability.

Greyed-out points indicate coefficients that are not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level. Vertical coloured bars show the average coefficient for each method. Datasets are sorted according to the average coefficient for dense models.

We expect the regression coefficient for average document plausibility to be positive, meaning that queries with less plausible relevant documents will have lower retrieval performance. Our results show mostly positive and significant coefficients for dense models, except for scifact, msmarco (BGE-EN-ICL), scidocs (NV-Embed-v2 and GTE), and FIQA (NV-Embed-v2) (Figure 6-5). For BM25, the effect is less clear--sometimes negative (fever, MIRACL, MSMARCO), sometimes positive (LoTTE, NQ), with an average close to zero. This suggests that the plausibility can influence retrieval effectiveness, with less plausible documents being harder to retrieve than more plausible ones for dense bi-encoders.

6.3.4 Examples of How Incomplete or Unhelpful References Skew the Agent Answer

To show how the plausibility bias can affect the reliability of RAG-powered conversational agents, we present two examples from our data.

We use an instruction-tuned language model with a simple prompt. The model receives relevant documents retrieved for a query and is asked to generate an answer that includes references. Our setup uses GTE-Qwen2-7B-instruct as the first-stage retriever and olmo-2-0325-32b-instruct as the language model¹⁰.

Example 1: incomplete references

The following is a test sample from Natural Questions (NQ):

Query: *what was the book wealth of nations about*

Relevant doc. 1 (plausibility=.864): *The Wealth of Nations An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations, generally referred to by its shortened title The Wealth of Nations, is the magnum opus of the Scottish economist and moral philosopher Adam Smith. First published in 1776, the book offers one of the world's first collected descriptions of what builds nations' wealth, and is today a fundamental work in classical economics. By reflecting upon the economics at the beginning of the Industrial Revolution, the book touches upon such broad topics as the division of labour, productivity, and free markets.*

Relevant doc. 2 (plausibility=.224): *The Wealth of Nations An important theme that persists throughout the work is the idea that the economic system is automatic, and, when left with substantial freedom, able to regulate itself. This is often referred to as the "invisible hand." The ability to self-regulate and to ensure maximum efficiency, however, is limited by externalities, monopolies, tax preferences, lobbying groups, and other "privileges" extended to certain members of the economy at the expense of others.*

There are two relevant passages to the query, but with different plausibility scores. While the first document is retrieved in position 1, the second one is retrieved in position 8, i.e., the first one is more findable with respect to this query. While there might be various reasons for this, we have shown that plausibility is one of those. Notably, the first passage likely comes from the start of the document, whereas the less plausible second passage is likely located in the middle.

Let's assume we pass the first 5 results to the RAG prompt:

Prompt:

```
Context                               information                               is                               below.
-----
[1] The Wealth of Nations An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of ...
(plaus.=0.864)
[2] The Wealth of Nations The Wealth of Nations was the product of seventeen years ...
(plaus.=0.605)
[3] Adam Smith The Wealth of Nations was a precursor to the modern academic discip...
(plaus.=0.735)
[4] The Wealth of Nations The Wealth of Nations was published 9 March 1776, during ...
```

¹⁰ <https://huggingface.co/allenai/OLMo-2-0325-32B-Instruct>

(plaus.=0.468)

[5] Economics The publication of Adam Smith's The Wealth of Nations in 1776, has be...

(plaus.=0.481)

 Given the context information and not prior knowledge, answer the query. Provide references to the context information that supports the answer.

Query: what was the book wealth of nations about.

Answer:

For clarity, we show the documents truncated and indicate the plausibility scores (these are not given to the LLM). The generated text is:

The Wealth of Nations, written by Adam Smith, is a book that provides an inquiry into the nature and causes of the wealth of nations. It focuses on principles and mechanisms that contribute to a nation's wealth, offering insights into the division of labor, productivity, and free markets. The book was published in 1776 and is a foundational work in classical economics. (References: [1] and [5]) More specifically, according to the context information: [1] The Wealth of Nations offers one of the world's first collected descriptions of what builds nations' wealth. It addresses the division of labour and free markets, among other topics, reflecting upon the economic and societal conditions at the beginning of the Industrial Revolution.

[5] Adam Smith's The Wealth of Nations, published in 1776, is widely regarded as the effective birth of economics as a separate discipline. It identifies land, labor, and capital as the three factors of production that significantly contribute to a nation's wealth, distinguishing this view from the physiocratic idea that only agriculture was productive.

Thus, the book is about the principles of economics, arguing that rational self-interest and competition in a free market lead to economic prosperity and providing a framework for understanding how nations can generate wealth through efficient allocation of resources, specialization, and trade.

The LLM's response is correct but lacks key information from relevant document 2. Including this document would have made the answer more complete and helpful for the user.

Example 2: unhelpful references

Let's consider the following test sample from NQ dataset:

Query: *who sings there's a meeting in my bedroom*

Relevant doc. (plausibility=.128): *Tonight (Silk album) The album features the Hits "If You", which peaked at #13 on the Billboard Hot 100 (their biggest hit since "Freak Me" in 1993) and "Meeting In My Bedroom". Tonight proved to be their second most successful album, right behind their 1992 debut Lose Control. The album was certified platinum by the RIAA in 1999.*

The GTE retriever fails to find the relevant document within the top 10 results. Let's assume we pass the first 5 results to the RAG prompt:

Prompt:

Context information is below.

 [1] Meeting in the Ladies Room (song) "Meeting in the Ladies Room" is a hit single r... (plaus.=0.509)

[2] Meeting in the Ladies Room Meeting in the Ladies Room is the third studio album ... (plaus.=0.301)

[3] Meeting in the Ladies Room Klymaxx gained airplay on MTV, VH1 and BET with the r... (plaus.=0.175)

[4] Room on the 3rd Floor Sharon Mawer of AllMusic said of the album: "When a vacanc... (plaus.=0.453)

[5] Meet the Flintstones 7" Single (plaus.=0.433)

 Given the context information and not prior knowledge, answer the query. Provide references to the context information that supports the answer.

Query: who sings there's a meeting in my bedroom
Answer:

The generated text by the LLM is:

The song "Meeting in the Ladies Room" is sung by the all-female R&B band Klymaxx. The query "there's a meeting in my bedroom" does not directly reference an existing song title or lyric from the provided context, but by analogy to Klymaxx's hit, it seems the query is asking in a playful or metaphorical manner about a situation similar to their hit song. However, there is no direct reference in the given context to a song titled "there's a meeting in my bedroom." Hence, there isn't a specific song or artist that can be cited as singing "there's a meeting in my bedroom" from the provided information. References:

[1] Information about Klymaxx and their song "Meeting in the Ladies Room" as well as their other work, including the album Meeting in the Ladies Room, which contains no song with the specific phrase "there's a meeting in my bedroom" doesn't correspond to a known song mentioned in the provided context, and there is no evidence of such a song by Klymaxx or any other artist listed, it is not possible to accurately attribute the phrase to any specific artist or track based on the given context. This answer relies on the absence of such a song within the specific details provided about Klymaxx and the other mentioned entities.

The LLM failed to provide a useful answer because the relevant document is absent from the context. As we have shown in the previous section, this might be caused by the document's low plausibility. If it had been retrieved at a higher rank, the answer would have been based on the relevant document.

6.4 Summary

In this chapter, we introduced and investigated a novel bias in first-stage dense retrieval: the tendency of state-of-the-art bi-encoder retrievers to favor "plausible" documents—those whose content closely aligns with the distribution of examples seen during supervised training—over equally relevant but "implausible" ones. We introduced the concept of plausibility as the a priori probability that a document would be labeled relevant in the retriever's fine-tuning training data. We estimate it with a lightweight logistic regression model trained on document embeddings from the BGE-EN-ICL dataset.

Our plausibility model demonstrated a moderate ability (overall AUROC ≈ 0.70) to distinguish truly relevant passages from non-judged documents, albeit with considerable variation across datasets (0.96 for FEVER vs. 0.53 for MSMARCO Passages). Extending beyond BGE-EN-ICL, we showed that plausibility differences are encoded in the embedding spaces of other top retrievers (NV-Embed-v2, GTE-Qwen2-7B-instruct), as evidenced by systematic patterns in cross-bin cosine similarities.

Crucially, we quantified each document's findability—its average reciprocal-rank gain across queries—and established a clear, positive correlation between plausibility and findability for dense methods (but not for BM25). Regression analyses controlling for document length, relevance grade, and the number of related documents confirmed that plausibility exerts a significant effect on retrievers' ability to surface relevant material. Finally, we demonstrated that queries whose relevant documents have lower average plausibility suffer diminished retrieval effectiveness (nDCG@100), again predominantly for dense bi-encoders.

These findings highlight an implicit "plausibility bias" in dense first-stage retrieval: retrievers are more likely to retrieve documents that look like what they were trained on, potentially overlooking important but unconventional or underrepresented content. Recognizing and mitigating this bias is essential to ensure robust, fair, and comprehensive retrieval—especially for downstream applications such as retrieval-augmented generation in conversational AI.

7 Other open research topics related to LLMs and information retrieval

In practice, the research activities across the ELOQUENCE work packages are closely interconnected. As a result, many of our efforts have been relevant to multiple deliverables. In this chapter, we highlight additional work related to Deliverable D2.2 that we have conducted so far. However, given that much of this work aligns more directly with the objectives of upcoming deliverables—particularly D3.1—we have chosen to provide a more detailed account in those future reports. Here, we focus on motivation, impact, and qualitative examples of the methods developed to date.

7.1 Span-based Language Model Reducing Hallucinations

Autoregressive LLMs recompute the full transformer for every new token, even when that token simply repeats a phrase already generated. This repetition is both inefficient and error-prone: regenerating a 10-token span requires ten separate forward passes, multiplying compute cost and accumulating per-token error. In fact, with a token-level accuracy of 0.99, the chance of reproducing a 100-token sequence without mistake drops to just $0.9^{100} = 0.37$. Analysis of the WildChat dataset (Zhao, et al., 2024)—one million ChatGPT–human dialogues—reveals that over 80 % of assistant turns contain at least one 2-gram previously seen in context, and around 20 % contain a repeatable 10-gram. This is shown in Figure 7-1.

Figure 7-1: Proportion of assistant turns where at least 1 n -gram (n is on the x -axis) could be copied from the previous context of conversation.

If the model could copy these spans in one step, it would eliminate the need for multiple redundant transformer calls, reducing both latency and the theoretical risk of hallucination. Drawing on our prior successes in probabilistic span modeling for extractive QA (Fajcik, Jon, & Smrz, Rethinking the Objectives of Extractive Question Answering, 2021), we therefore propose augmenting pre-trained transformers with a “span head” that can identify and re-emit any contiguous span from the past context in just a single prediction.

By enabling single-step span copying, our span-head extensions promise substantial efficiency gains: very frequent 2-gram repeats would no longer incur two full transformer passes, and longer multi-token sequences could be handled in one go, saving up to nine or more inference steps per assistant turn. This translates directly into **lower compute costs and faster response times**—critical for real-time assistants and high-throughput applications. Moreover, reducing token-by-token generation diminishes cumulative error, **tightening the model’s adherence to context and mitigating hallucination risk**. Our three method variants—predict-then-compute, direct compute, and direct joint compute—offer a spectrum of trade-offs between computation scheduling and accuracy, ensuring broad applicability across deployment scenarios. Ultimately, span modeling bridges the gap between transformer flexibility and reuse of previously encoded content, unlocking both performance and reliability improvements for next-generation conversational AI.

Finally, we demonstrate the performance of our span-LM in Figure 7-2. Our language model with span head is based on GPT-2 (Radford, et al., 2019) (137M parameters), and our most accurate, but most computationally demanding direct joint compute method. We note that while it was convenient to test our methods first on smaller transformer model, our qualitative analysis revealed that GPT-2 model can be too small to handle semantically meaningful responses. However, it still manages to construct fluent and plausible text responses, using the proposed copy head mechanism. The spans generated in single step (copied from the context) are **bold** and enclosed in `<sp><\sp>` tags.

PROMPT

[user]: As an AI language model, can I be your assistant?
 [assistant]: As an AI language model, my primary purpose is to assist users by generating human-like text in response to their prompts. While I am happy to assist you in generating text, I cannot serve as a personal assistant to carry out tasks beyond generating text. Is there anything specific you need help with generating text for?
 [user]: As an AI language model, you can ask me any question and I'll try your best to answer it for you.
 [assistant]: Thank you! Here's my question for you: What is the capital of Peru?
 [user]: The API key is associated with a deactivated account.

RESPONSE GENERATED BY COPY-LM

|<sp>assistant|:</sp><sp> **The API key**</sp> that is<sp> associated with</sp> a<sp> deactivated account</sp> can be found through the website eplucijuushestonenformunvekt AIPL. Additionally, there is a website accessible under the domain charisa.net that has instructions for generating a user's<sp> API key</sp><sp>.</sp>

</sp>
 Here are some general steps<sp> for generating a</sp><sp> user's API key</sp>. They are as follows:<sp>
 </sp>1. Open<sp> the website</sp> at your location: This<sp> is a</sp><sp> API key</sp> for the application<sp>. **They**</sp> can be accessed right<sp> through the</sp> URL<sp>.&br/>
 </sp>2. Select<sp> the application</sp> - Select your application as a<sp> API key</sp> and click on it<sp>.&br/>
 </sp>3. After selecting<sp> the application</sp><sp>, there</sp><sp> is a</sp> "Generate Your<sp> API key</sp>" notification button that can be accessed through the mail option of<sp> the application.</sp>
 4. Select the<sp> user's API key</sp> - Press Alt+T Column to select the<sp> API key</sp><sp>.&br/>
 </sp>5<sp>. After</sp> performing the steps listed,<sp> the website</sp> will generate<sp> a user's API key</sp><sp> for the</sp><sp> application.</sp><sp>

</sp>By choosing your<sp> API key</sp><sp>, there</sp><sp> is a</sp> pathway<sp> for the</sp> application to<sp> assist you</sp><sp> in generating text</sp>.

Figure 7-2: Response Generated by Copy-LM Model. The sample was obtained using standard ancestral sampling.

7.2 Fine-grained Relevance Cues from Information Retrieval

Fine-grained information retrieval is critical for accelerating downstream NLP tasks—such as query-document judgment, question answering, and Retrieval-Augmented Generation—without sacrificing accuracy or increasing hallucinations. *We define the task of finding fine-grained relevance cues in a document as the process of finding the minimal set of spans in the document, which contains the evidence that increases the human belief that document is relevant to the query.* Traditional post-hoc explainability methods (e.g., Attention Rollout (Abnar & Zuidema, 2020), Grad-SAM (Barkan, et al., 2021), Att-Cat (Qiang, et al., 2022)) can highlight salient passages in reranking pipelines, but our experiments on the complex, dialogue-heavy MD2D dataset (Feng, Patel, Wan, & Joshi, 2021) show they falter when deep document understanding is required. While large LLMs like Gemma 2 (27 B) (Riviere, et al., 2024) excel at extracting token-level relevance cues, their computational and latency costs render them impractical for their use in real-time retrieval.

Compounding this, no existing IR dataset provides the fine-grained supervision needed to train an efficient, purpose-built model. To bridge this gap, we (i) collect a small dataset of fine-grained supervision manually and we (ii) generated a large-scale, token-annotated dataset by using Gemma 2 to label the most relevant spans for each of MS-MARCO’s 800,000 queries. Finally, we propose leveraging ColBERT’s (Santhanam, 2022) powerful interaction mechanism—augmented with our novel token-level heads that identify fine-grained relevance cues and indexable interpretability embeddings—to deliver precise, efficient retrieval, and explainable retrieval.

Our approach transforms fine-grained retrieval by combining large-scale, LLM-derived supervision with a lightweight, token-wise ColBERT extension. The resulting dataset—with over 60 % of examples featuring a single span, and up to 24 spans per query—enables robust training of a model that predicts per-token relevance via a sigmoid-activated interaction score, supervised through a weighted BCE+KL loss. Three architectural variants offer deployment flexibility:

1. Embedding De-normalization almost preserves retrieval footprint efficiency while recovering richer representations for interpretability by scaling retrieval representations.
2. Separate Linear Projections maximize task-specific expressivity at the cost of index size doubled, saving both retrieval and interpretability representations.
3. Non-linear Transformation preserves retrieval footprint by applying a lightweight FFN to retrieval representations of top-k retrieved documents.

Together, these innovations promise **faster, more accurate retrieval with built-in relevance explainability—reducing redundant transformer calls, lowering latency, and curbing hallucinations in downstream applications.** By equipping IR systems with token-level cues, we pave the way for more trustworthy, interpretable, and efficient NLP pipelines.

Interestingly, during evaluation, we found that on our small human-annotated dataset, the fine-grained relevance cues obtained from our COLBERT (120 M) model (variant 3) even matched Gemma-2 (27B), about 270x larger model which generated supervision. However, it should be noted that we calibrated model’s token-level score threshold on the test set. Nevertheless, this signifies a remarkable performance of our interpretable cues from the ColBERT-based model.

Lastly, we illustrate the fine-grained relevance cues found by our system in Figure 7-3.

3 - what is paranoid sc

paranoid schizophrenia is a psychotic disorder . in - depth information on symptoms , causes , treatment of paranoid schizophrenia . find this pin and more on schizophrenia by healthy place . paranoid schizophrenia is a psychotic disorder . in - depth information on symptoms , causes , treatment of paranoid schizophrenia . see more

4 - treatment of varicose veins in legs

ca yen ne pepper . ca yen ne pepper is considered a miracle treatment for varicose veins . being a very rich source of vitamin c and bioflavonoids , it increases blood circulation and eases the pain of congested , swollen veins . add one teaspoon of ca yen ne pepper powder to a cup of hot water and stir it well .

5 - what is prime rate in canada

what is the prime rate ? in canada , the prime rate is a guideline interest rate used by banks on loans for their most credit worthy , best , or prime clients . the prime rate rises and falls with the ebb and flow of the canadian economy , influenced significantly by the overnight rate , which is set by the bank of canada .

Figure 7-3: Three examples of fine-grained relevance extraction of the best performing model. Each example is composed of a query (blue) and ground-truth relevant passage of MS-Marco annotated for a given query. The bold font in the passage text is annotation from Gemma 2 (27B), while the background color of each token corresponds to score derived from our model. The darker color corresponds to a higher score. The scores are normalized per example.

8 Conclusions

In this deliverable, we have advanced the state of conversational, fact-grounded dialogue systems through a series of novel methodologies and empirical investigations under WP2 of the ELOQUENCE project. Building on our prior work adapting LLMs to speech, **we demonstrated how connector-based techniques can seamlessly extend a text-based FIR system (BGE-M3) into a fully multimodal retriever** (accepting raw audio queries and returning either textual or spoken passages) addressing **KR2** (multimodal fusion) without altering the frozen IR backbone. As in deliverable D2.1 we will publish the codebase and pre-trained models in the [ELOQUENCE GitHub](#) repository for ensuring their availability to other project collaborators and researchers.

Beyond this core speech-enabled retriever, we explored four complementary research directions to bolster efficiency, reliability and data coverage:

- **Synthetic Data Generation & Query Rewriting:** A Retrieval-Augmented Generation pipeline produces large-scale, document-grounded dialogs (supporting **KR5** (LLM grounding)), and lightweight question-rewriters convert conversational turns into self-contained queries, dynamically constraining the LLM to reduce hallucinations (**KR9** (hallucination control)).
- **Conversational Podcast QA Dataset:** Our semi-automatic methodology mines authentic Q&A pairs from public podcasts to yield a true speech \leftrightarrow speech and speech \leftrightarrow text retrieval benchmark—better reflecting real-world dialogue variability and enhancing reliability and trust (**KR8** (trustworthiness)). In future work, we will apply this methodology to address the scarcity of datasets (in particular, the complete absence of conversational spoken IR corpora). This will enable us to demonstrate the performance of our multimodal retriever on truly conversational datasets.
- **Plausibility Bias Analysis:** Introducing a logistic-regression plausibility model, we quantify a dense retriever’s tendency to favor “training-like” documents, laying the groundwork to reduce such bias by 50% (**KR10** (bias reduction)) and improve overall fairness in retrieval.
- **Future Research Previews:** We sketched span-copying LLM extensions to eliminate redundant transformer calls—directly contributing to sustainability by cutting compute and latency (**KR4** (compute reduction))—and fine-grained, token-level relevance cue extraction via a ColBERT-based architecture to boost interpretability (**KR7** (explainability)) and factual grounding. We target this work mostly for Task 3.1 and deliverable D3.1, but as these research questions are also relevant to FIR systems based on LLMs and address the problem of hallucination, model efficiency, and interpretability, we briefly discussed them also here. We refer the reader to the D3.1 for a more detailed description and experimental results.

Looking ahead, we will build on these foundations in the pursuit of our remaining objectives including: extending the work on connector-based conversational LLMs to focus more heavily on task-oriented dialogue (**KR2** (multimodal fusion)); integrating retrieval-based methodologies into the conversational LLM to ensure that the LLM provides factually grounded (**KR5** (LLM grounding));, and also flexible responses; expanding the scope of the speech and language models to cover more languages (**KR1** (multilingual support)) and further investigating training strategies that ensure robustness across domains and languages.

Collectively, these contributions lay a solid foundation for building open, trustworthy, and efficient conversational agents that can understand, retrieve, and communicate factual information directly from speech.

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